

Two-Stage Conversion of GA Drawings into 3D Model Using Deep Learning

Jisang Ha, NTNU, Ålesund/Norway, jisang.ha@ntnu.no
Henrique Gaspar, NTNU, Ålesund/Norway, henrique.gaspar@ntnu.no

Abstract

This study explores the conversion of 2D General Arrangement (GA) drawings of ships into 3D arrangement models using deep learning. We start investigating the current status of key AI/deep learning tools available, such as ChatGPT, YOLO, DETR, and SAM, for our case. Our main study is performed using SAM, by a two-stage process: firstly, performing segmentation and extracting data from GA images. Secondly, combining data into a 3D model of a ship. Compared to the other tools or methods, which failed to function properly and had limitations, our approach successfully operated in recognizing GAs and extracting data. The approach was validated using GAs of commercial vessels, especially tankers. These results are expected to improve the utilization of 2D drawings currently used in shipyards and increase the connectivity and integration between early-stage ship design and later stages of work.

1. 3D from 2D GAs and the role of reverse engineering a hull

Reverse engineering is understood in the broader engineering and product development domains as the process of deconstructing an artifact - whether a machine, structure, or document - to extract design information, *Hess (2022)*. For the sake of our paper, the scope is narrowed as the methodology of extracting design knowledge from existing documentation when the original models are not available, *Legaz and Gaspar (2024)*. In the context of this paper, reverse engineering does not necessarily rely on physical measurements or 3D scanning, but rather on analyzing technical drawings, such as General Arrangement (GA).

This approach is particularly relevant for academic research, where GAs published in sources like RINA's Significant Ships series, *RINA (2019)*, or preserved in archives as scanned drawings, often represent the only accessible design information. In the case of ships' GAs, the process begins with extracting geometric and arrangement information directly from PDF files or scanned images. The goal is to reconstruct essential parameters, such as principal dimensions, compartmentation, or equipment layout, that enable further analysis.

Unlike 3D scanning, which captures the geometry of physical objects, GA reverse engineering relies on careful interpretation of scaled drawings, annotations, and available metadata. Through digital processing - vectorization, scaling, or CAD re-drawing - these documents can be transformed into usable models. Such reconstructed models support academic studies, benchmarking, and comparative analyses, particularly when investigating historical vessels or ships where design data is otherwise inaccessible.

The aim of our incipient research is to develop a AI-supported re-engineering process able to convert hull from 2D GA to a 3D model. This is expected to significantly assist designers by integrating the fragmented 2D drawings and 3D models that exist at each stage of ship design. Specifically, it expects to extract the ship's hull as a 3D model from a 2D low resolution GA drawings.

We tested some of the the current AI tools before committing to SAM (Segment Anything Model). The first approach was an LLM, represented by ChatGPT. Drawing recognition via LLM worked successfully only for the text when a separate text layer existed in the drawing, and it still had difficulties understanding context when images and text coexisted. The second approach was a method of using image recognition models, commonly employed for drawing recognition. This approach required a very large amount of drawing data as a training set to address the domain shift. However, ship drawings have

relatively scarce training data; therefore, they showed low performance. After these attempts, we concluded that an approach based on segmentation models achieved the highest performance in ship GA. We performed segmentation and extracted data from GA images using SAM. Then, we involved combining the extracted data into a 3D model of a ship as the next stage. Through this approach, we were successfully able to perform the conversion from 2D drawings to 3D models. This is presented as follows.

2. Current Limitations on the Recognition of GA Using LLM and Image Recognition

2.1. Using LLM for Recognition of GA

For the conversion of 2D General Arrangement (GA), we can firstly consider utilizing Large Language Model (LLM) to recognize GA. Fig.1 shows the result of requesting a mock-up version of the GA of NTNU's research vessel “Gunnerus” to be input and reproduced as a 2D graph. (ChatGPT 4o) “Analyze the differences between the two designs.”

Fig.1: Results of GA recognition by LLM (ChatGPT 4o)

In Fig.1, ChatGPT failed to recognize several information. In Fig.1(1), max_40 appears before min_30, and other figures also show similar issues. Furthermore, it often confuses certain information with the names of arrangements. Other LLMs, such as llama 3.2, also show similar results. However, results obtained using only LLMs often fail to consider the text written on the image (drawing) or mistakenly identify the text as part of the image. Fig.2 is an example of extracting only the text layer from the same drawing and re-extracting only the ship's arrangement and hull information.

If the drawing is in a file format such as PDF or DWG that has a separate text layer, the required data could be successfully extracted as shown in Fig.2. However, the problem is that even if designers use the appropriate format, they often fail to separate all text layers. Furthermore, layers frequently become fragmented when handled by multiple designers. Therefore, recent attempts have been made to improve recognition rates when images and text coexist by utilizing LLM and text recognition algorithms (such as OCR technologies) together. *Chen (n.d.)* attempted to improve results by utilizing Tesseract OCR (Optical Character Recognition) on some images, such as receipts, rather than using LLM alone.

Design Comparison Table: RV Gunnerus (Before vs After Rebuild)

Space	Old Design Location/Size (1463114)	New Design Location/Size (165821B6)	Change Summary
Engine Room	Aft lower section (below 1st deck), approx. 9.60×4.20 m (≈31.3 m ²)	Similar position, slightly extended aft, almost same size	Minimal change in size. Slightly shifted aft due to hull extension.
Sludge Tank	Near engine room, 1.7 m ³	Same location, 1.7 m ³	No change in volume.
Bilge Tank	Bottom of engine room, 3.5 m ³	Same location, 3.5 m ³	No change in volume.
Fresh Water Tank	Midship (below), 11.2 m ³	Midship (expanded section), 17.0 m ³	Volume increased by approx. +5.8 m ³ . New tank or expansion added in lengthened area.
Black/Grey Water Tanks	Black: 3.2 m ³ , Grey: 3.2 m ³	Same: Black 3.2 m ³ , Grey 3.2 m ³	No change in volume or location.
Oil Waste Tank	Near engine room, 1.8 m ³	Same: 1.8 m ³	No change in volume.
Cargo Hold	Mid-upper section, 21.2 m ³	Mid-upper section, 21.2 m ³	Same volume. Slight aft shift due to hull lengthening.
Ballast / Roll Damping Tanks	Ballast only: 47.8 m ³ total (No.12: 5.0 + No.13sb: 5.0 + No.13p: 37.8)	Same ballast capacity: 47.8 m ³ + New Roll Damping Tank: 21.2 m³	Roll damping tank added. Ballast tank sizes unchanged, but geometry adjusted.
Bridge / Control Room	Superstructure center top (approx. 15 m ²)	Same area, shifted slightly aft	Same function and size. Repositioned aft with new superstructure layout.
Accommodation / Labs / Conf. Room	A-deck: Conf. Room 20 m ² , others not precisely listed	A-deck: Conf. Room 20 m ² + New Lab (Dry Lab 8.5 m²) , tech rooms	Existing conference room kept. New technical/lab areas added such as Dry Lab (8.5 m ²).

Fig.2: Extracted data from the text layer of the drawing

In this study, considering the characteristics of ship's GA, which consists of a mixture of various images, texts, and information, we aim to recognize the components of GA and extract information by attempting various types of image recognition deep learning technologies.

2.2. Using Image Recognition Models for Recognition of GA

There are several representative models commonly used for image recognition, e.g., YOLO and DETR. YOLO (You Only Look Once), *Redmon et al. (2016)*, is a model for image recognition that was first proposed in 2016 and has evolved into more than 12 different versions, including YOLOv12. DETR (Detection Transformers), *Carion et al. (2020)*, is an image recognition model proposed by Facebook AI Research that utilizes a transformer-based architecture to achieve good results in image recognition. The following figure shows the results of attempting ship hull recognition or arrangement recognition using image recognition with different models.

Image recognition results using YOLO and DETR for GA drawing did not perform consistently well, Fig.3. It failed to recognize intended objects or the ship hull, and even after setting new classes and training the model, we observed that the original classes were recognized incorrectly more frequently. This is the domain shift problem that occurs when applying such AI models to a different target domain with which they were trained, and it arises when tuning or retraining with a small number of images. For image recognition approaches, accumulating a larger dataset of over 10,000 images is expected to be necessary to extract meaningful data from GA for constructing 3D models. While studies have utilized various models beyond the one we present, *Stensrud and Klausen (2022)*, many are attempting to recognize drawings using new approaches. Segmentation models are one of the novel approaches

that performed better than image recognition approaches when targeting ship drawings. The results of tuning and training the best-performing model, SAM 2.1, *Ravi et al. (2024)*, are introduced in the next chapter.

Fig.3: Image recognition results by YOLOv12x (1) and DETR (2)

3. Two-Stage Conversion of GA Drawings into 3D Model Using Deep Learning

3.1. The Process of Two-Stage Conversion of GA Drawings into 3D Model

In this section, we introduce our process of two-stage conversion of GA drawings into 3D model using deep learning techniques. Fig.4 illustrates the entire process.

Fig.4: The process of two-stage conversion of GA drawings into 3D model

The procedure is represented in Fig.4, in which each number represents the sequential order in which each process is executed, and the dotted lines indicate functions that are planned but not yet implemented. Throughout this entire application, we connected and displayed all input and output results through the web application, Fig.4(1). As input, we used publicly available GAs from digital versions of *RINA (2013-2018)*. We used the information on the ship specifications (task 2-(1)) within GA and the figures for the midship section (task 2-(2)) and profile view (task 2-(3)) as input for our model.

Fig.4(3) illustrates the first stage of the conversion. The first stage recognizes the hull from GA drawings using image segmentation. To achieve this, the study separated and processed the midship section drawing and the ship longitudinal profile drawing for recognition and segmentation. For image recognition and segmentation, various published models such as YOLO, DETR, and SAM were tested. Among these, SAM 2.1, which showed the best results, was selected and trained using GA. We separated the midship section image (task 3-(1)) and profile view image (task 3-(2)) into distinct datasets for training to achieve better results, extracting information from each drawing.

The second stage, Fig.4(4) involves creating a 3D model based on the results from the first stage. By expanding the ship's shape identified from the midship section image along the lines obtained from the profile drawing, a ship 3D model was generated with lines and offsets.

As output, we created a 3D model of the ship hull accessible via a web application and calculated the vessel's basic volume and coefficients for user verification.

3.2. Recognition of Midship Section

We start with task 3-1 using the SAM2.1 model, which proved most effective at segmentation of hulls in GA drawings. The results of the SAM2.1_large model's recognition of the midship section, performed without any training or tuning, are shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Results of segmentation and recognition of ship hulls from midship section drawings (Before training)

In Fig.5, we input the drawing image into the model as input, and the area rendered in blue represents the region the model predicted to be the ship hull. We highlighted certain characteristic errors in red. Fig.5(1) successfully performed segmentation, but since it was performed without superstructure knowledge and learning about ship hulls and other parts, it recognized all figure areas as a single object. Fig.5(2) performed relatively successfully but still failed to recognize some areas properly. Fig.5(3) shows the same problems as those found in LLM and other networks. When text explaining the figure is present around it, the text is often recognized as part of the figure or as a single object. In the case of Fig.5(4), the model confused tanks or arrangements inside the ship hull with the ship hull. The results of 34 GAs are summarized in the Table I.

Table I: Summary of the results of midship section (Before training)

Max. Width error (px)	Max. Height error (px)	Average error of width	Average error of height
238	151	36.6%	37.9%

The following is an example of the segmentation results obtained by performing segmentation using a model trained with RINA's data.

Fig.6: Results of segmentation and recognition of ship hulls from midship section drawings (After training)

In Fig.6, all the issues encountered in Fig.5 have been resolved. Segmentation was performed only on the ship hull, excluding superstructures. Fig.6(2) showed good results despite containing both figures and various texts. Fig.5(3) also successfully excluded the superstructure. The summarized results after the training are in Table III.

Table II: Summary of the results of midship section (After training)

Max. Width error (px)	Max. Height error (px)	Average error of width	Average error of height
14	27	1.70%	2.61%

Fig.7: An example of recognition of midship section

Problems still occur in scenarios like Fig.7. When a grid for the crane or cargo is drawn in the midsection, the model sometimes misinterprets it. The errors in width and height are the result of this, and excluding these examples has a similar error rate with width, approximately 1.71%.

3.3. Recognition of Profile View

For task 3-2, the SAM2.1_large model, as described in Section 3.1 and Fig.4, was applied to the profile view of the ship GA. The number of ship GAs used for training is the same as task 3-1 (in Section 3.2).

An example of the results is shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8: An example of recognition of profile view

Ship hulls are generally well recognized and can be segmented by GA, but accuracy tends to decrease when multiple superstructures are found. The summarized results after the training are in Table III.

Table III: Summary of the results of profile view (After training)

Max. Width error (px)	Max. Height error (px)	Average error of width	Average error of height
130	1308	34.7%	40.6%

Despite showing good results in Fig.8, the poor performance in Table III is due to our current model being trained with a bias toward specific ship types. While it achieves very high accuracy for ship hulls like tankers, it performs poorly with high error rates for passenger ships or other hull types.

4. Application Using the Proposed Method

We created a 3D model as task 4, using the method proposed in Section 3, with the midship section view and profile view of the ship GA as input. The target vessel is an ore carrier from *RINA (2018)*. Figs.9 and 10 show the results of recognizing the vessel's GA and representing it with points and lines.

Fig.9: An example of recognition of GA

The midship section, Fig.9(1), and profile view, Fig.9(2), images were input, with the blue area representing the point predicted as the ship hull by task 3. Representing this again with more refined points and lines are in Fig.10.

Fig.10: An example of recognition results expressed as points and lines

For Task 4, we extracted only the ship hull portion below the draft from the results of Task 3 (Figs.9 and 10), expanded it into 3D, and connected the pieces. The result is shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11: An example of hull 3D model from GA

Based on the model obtained, displacement and the block coefficient (C_b) are estimated. The comparison results are shown in Table IV. The ship's C_b could be estimated with an error of approximately 3.9%. However, this estimation is performed on a ship with a large C_b and a simple hull form. For ships of various hull types, the accuracy can be potentially lower.

Table IV: Summary of the results of a 3D model

	Displacement (ton)	C_b
Actual ship	453,463.2	0.8323 @23.0
Generated model	435,865	0.80

Fig.12: An example of the web application

Fig.12 shows an incipient example of the configured web application. (At the time of the submission of the article, the web application is being developed, therefore the irregular 3D version observed. We expect to have a smoother version running by the day of the conference.) When the GA drawing is entered as input, the 2D segmentation results for that figure are displayed at the bottom according to the page, and the 3D model is generated and displayed at the top.

5. Conclusions

Reverse engineering of GAs through computer vision provides a practical method to extract editable geometries when original design models are unavailable. This process can also be extended to onboard applications, where visual data capture may substitute for additional sensors.

Progress in this area will depend on collaborative efforts between academia, industry, and regulatory bodies to establish reliable methods, evaluate limitations, and define standards. Attention to cybersecurity will remain important, since the same technologies can be misused if not properly safeguarded. We suggest the same approach as *Legaz et al. (2025)*: training the model right while training the right model.

Training the Model Right: When applying computer vision and AI techniques to reverse engineer ship GA drawings, the quality of training data and the process of model development are decisive. Unlike physical 3D scans, GAs exist as technical documents with varied formats - ranging from vector-based PDFs to scanned raster images. Training the model right therefore requires datasets that capture this diversity and reflect the specific conventions of naval architecture drawings. Without such domain-specific data, generic computer vision models risk misinterpreting or omitting critical features. Open datasets of ship drawings, coupled with transparent annotation protocols, can help establish a foundation for reliable feature extraction. Expert validation is paramount, ensuring that the AI correctly identifies ship compartments, machinery spaces, and arrangement details in line with established design practices.

Training the Right Model: Beyond training quality, it is also necessary to ensure that the models themselves are suited to handle GAs as use case. Models developed for generic document analysis or architectural plans may not account for the conventions and standards of ship design. Training the right model involves tailoring architectures and workflows specifically for maritime drawings. This includes incorporating recognition modules for ship-specific symbols, multi-scale analysis to handle both global dimensions and fine details, and alignment with classification schemes used in ship registers and regulatory documents. Validation against reference vessels and cross-checks with hydrostatic or stability data can ensure that the extracted GA information is not only geometrically consistent but also meaningful for subsequent analyses.

In the case of GAs, progress will require both strategies: training the model right, with carefully curated and annotated datasets, and training the right model, with methods adapted to the characteristics of ship design drawings.

Moreover, there is still potential for error correction in the process of building the 3D model by synthesizing the information. Furthermore, while the current process requires manual separation and input of the GA, future research aims to enable the construction of a 3D model solely by inputting the GA through combination with LLM models.

The results are expected to improve the utilization of 2D drawings currently used in shipyards and increase the connectivity and integration between early-stage ship design and later stages of work with the automation of GA reverse engineering and support reliable reuse of legacy documentation in maritime research and education.

References

- CARION, N.; MASSA, F.; SYNNAEVE, G.; USUNIER, N.; KIRILLOV, A.; ZAGORUYKO, S. (2020), *End-to-End Object Detection with Transformers*, <https://github.com/facebookresearch/detr>
- CHEN, J. (n.d.), *Enhancing Image Text Extraction with LLM and OCR*, https://medium.com/@jameschen_78678/enhancing-image-text-extraction-with-llm-and-ocr-8221cb555cc5
- HESS, B. (2022), *What is reverse engineering and how does it work?*, Technical report, Astromachine Works, <https://astromachineworks.com/what-is-reverse-engineering/>
- LEGAZ, M.J.; GASPAR, H.M. (2024), *Computer vision for reverse engineering in the design, simulation and operation of maritime systems*, European Council for Modelling and Simulation, ECMS, 38(1), pp.234–241
- LEGAZ, M.J.; GASPAR, H.M.; ICHINOSE, Y. (2025), *Open software for teaching and research maritime design and engineering*, ECMS, <https://doi.org/10.7148/2025-0039>
- RAVI, N.; GABEUR, V.; HU, Y.-T.; HU, R.; RYALI, C.; MA, T.; KHEDR, H.; RÄDLE, R.; ROLLAND, C.; GUSTAFSON, L.; MINTUN, E.; PAN, J.; VASUDEV ALWALA, K.; CARION, N.; WU, C.-Y.; GIRSHICK, R.; DOLLÁR, P.; FEICHTENHOFER, C.; FAIR, M. (2024), *SAM 2: Segment Anything in Images and Videos*, 13th Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR), pp.41175–41218, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2408.00714>
- REDMON, J.; DIVVALA, S.; GIRSHICK, R.; FARHADI, A. (2016), *You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection*, pp.779–788, <http://pjreddie.com/yolo/>
- RINA (2019), *Significant Ships of 2018*, The Royal Institution of Naval Architects, London
- STENSRUD, E.; KLAUSEN, K. (2022), *Another Step towards Remote Inspections of Maritime Vessels using Tailored Inspection Drones Instrumented with Computer Vision*, <https://utkilen.no/fleet/core-trade>